

Predicting the Underwater Blast Response of Sandwich Plates with Elastic Cores

Andreas Schiffer

Department of Mechanical Engineering
 Khalifa University, Abu Dhabi, UAE

Vito Tagarielli

Department of Aeronautics
 Imperial College London, UK

An important consideration in the design of naval ships and submarines is their resistance to withstand intense dynamic loading in the event of an explosion in water. Recent experimental, theoretical and numerical studies have found that sandwich construction offers significant advantages over monolithic designs in terms of underwater blast resistance, if a relatively soft and crushable core material is used, e.g. polymeric or metallic foams [1-7]. The reason for this lies mainly in the interaction between the moving structure and the adjacent fluid. However, if stronger cores are employed (e.g. metal honeycomb), fluid-structure interaction (FSI) phenomena are dictated by elastic deformation processes rather than by plastic crushing of the foam. This interaction significantly affects the response of the sandwich and gives rise to a series of cavitation phenomena which have not been studied in detail in the literature to date.

In this study, we fill this gap in the literature by developing one-dimensional (1D) analytical FSI models able to predict the underwater blast response of sandwich plates with elastically deforming cores, as well as the ensuing cavitation phenomena triggered by FSI. The presence of a non-negligible initial hydrostatic pressure will also be considered in our calculations, to account for the effect of deep water. In our analysis, we consider sandwich plates composed of an elastic core of stiffness k (per unit area) and two face sheets of equal areal mass m , as sketched in Fig. 1; both face sheets are in contact with water (density ρ_w) at initial static pressure p_{st} . The sandwich is loaded by an underwater blast wave, propagating in the adjacent water towards the structure and impinging on the front face sheet (Fig. 1). At sufficient distance from the detonation point, such blast wave can be considered as a 1D shock wave which decays exponentially (see Fig. 1) and propagates in the fluid at approximately sonic speed, c_w [8]. Hence, the problem considered here is a realistic 1D representation of blast loading on a real sandwich structure for the case of a non-contact explosion in water. Note that the peak pressure p_0 and decay time θ are set by the characteristics of the blast [8, 9].

Fig. 1 Schematic of problem geometry and loading conditions

The severity of the load imparted by the blast is strongly affected by water cavitation manifested in propagating phase fronts [10], also called breaking and closing fronts [11], acting as reflecting interfaces and affecting the pressure applied on the structure by the incident wave. This is implemented in our calculations by following the approach of Schiffer et al. [12] where two successive stages of response are considered: the response prior to the onset of cavitation in the water (*Stage I*) and subsequent to this event (*Stage II*). In *Stage I*, the fluid pressure is proportional to the volumetric compressive strain, which allows solving the governing equations of motion in closed form. In *Stage II*, Kennard's hydrodynamic equations [11] are employed to calculate explicitly the propagation of cavitation fronts in the water and their effect on the fluid pressure field which is used to compute face sheet motion, core compression and imparted impulse via numerical time integration. The developed equations allow identifying the governing non-dimensional parameters of the problem: non-dimensional face sheet mass ψ , core stiffness κ and initial hydrostatic pressure, \bar{p}_{st} .

As previous studies have shown [1-7], the response of a sandwich plate to underwater blast loading is highly sensitive to the sequence of cavitation phenomena triggered by FSI. The coupling of front and back face sheets through the elastic core gives rise to more complex cavitation phenomena than previously reported in the literature [12]. For the problem investigated here, three characteristic regimes of behavior are defined, according to the details of the cavitation process. We refer to Regime 1 in the event of double cavitation with two spatially separate cavitation processes occurring at the same time, while we denote as Regime 2 all responses where only one cavitation event takes place; finally, if cavitation is fully suppressed by the presence of a sufficiently high hydrostatic pressure, we refer to Regime 3. The regime charts in Fig. 2 can be used to determine the active regime of behaviour for a given set of non-dimensional parameters κ , ψ and \bar{p}_{st} .

Fig. 2 Non-dimensional regime charts in the κ - ψ space showing the regime transitions for $p_{st}/p_0 = 0$ (a) and $p_{st}/p_0 = 0.13$ (b).

To validate the predictions obtained with the analytical model, fully-coupled dynamic FE calculations were performed in ABAQUS/Explicit. As seen from Fig. 3, FE predictions of the cavitation front propagation (Fig. 3a) as well as of the structural response (Fig. 3b) were found to be in excellent agreement with those obtained with the analytical model for the case $\kappa = 5$, $\psi = 18$ and $p_{st} = 0$. Good agreement between the two types of predictions was also reported for a large range of parameters (see Fig. 4) concluding that our analytical model is able to predict the structural and fluid response with high accuracy and minimal computational cost (computation time less than 40 s on a standard desktop).

Fig. 3 Comparison of FE and analytical predictions for a Regime 2 response performed with $\kappa = 5$, $\psi = 18$ and $p_{st} = 0$: (a) trajectories of breaking fronts (BF) and closing fronts (CF); (b) time histories of face sheet velocities (in non-dimensional terms).

Finally, the validated analytical model was used to examine the effects of non-dimensional core stiffness κ , face sheet mass ψ and initial hydrostatic pressure \bar{p}_{st} to the impulse imparted to the sandwich, I_f , which quantifies the severity of blast loading. The results clearly show (see Fig. 4a) that the imparted impulse decreases if the core stiffness κ increases, suggesting that sandwich panels with stiff cores outperform those with soft cores in terms of blast resistance. It was also shown that the effect of core elasticity decreases with increasing hydrostatic pressure \bar{p}_{st} (see Fig. 4b), concluding that the advantage of using low stiffness cores is more pronounced in shallow water than in deep water.

Fig. 4 Analytical and FE predictions of non-dimensional impulse I_f / I_0 as functions of non-dimensional mass ψ (a) and initial hydrostatic pressure p_{st} / p_0 (b); $I_0 = 2p_0\theta$.

Keywords: fluid-structure interaction, blast loading, finite elements, cavitation

References:

- [1] V.S. Deshpande, N.A. Fleck, One-dimensional response of sandwich plates to underwater shock loading, *J. Mech. Phys. Solids*, 53 (2005) 2347-2383.
- [2] V.S. Deshpande, A. Heaver, N.A. Fleck, An underwater shock simulator, *P. Roy. Soc. Lond. A Mat.*, 462 (2006) 1021-1041.
- [3] A. Schiffer, V.L. Tagarielli, One-Dimensional Response of Sandwich Plates to Underwater Blast: Fluid-Structure Interaction Experiments and Simulations, *Int. J. Impact Eng.*, 71 (2014) 34-49.
- [4] M.T. Tilbrook, V.S. Deshpande, N.A. Fleck, Underwater blast loading of sandwich beams: Regimes of behaviour, *Int. J. Solids Struct.*, 46 (2009) 3209-3221.
- [5] H. Wadley, K. Dharmasena, Y. Chen, P. Dudt, D. Knight, R. Charette, K. Kiddy, Compressive response of multilayered pyramidal lattices during underwater shock loading, *Int. J. Impact Eng.*, 35 (2008) 1102-1114.
- [6] Z. Wei, K.P. Dharmasena, H.N.G. Wadley, A.G. Evans, Analysis and interpretation of a test for characterizing the response of sandwich panels to water blast, *Int. J. Impact Eng.*, 34 (2007) 1602-1618.
- [7] Z. Xue, J.W. Hutchinson, A comparative study of impulse-resistant metal sandwich plates, *Int. J. Impact Eng.*, 30 (2004) 1283-1305.
- [8] R.H. Cole, *Underwater Explosions*, Princeton University Press, Princeton, NJ, USA, 1948.
- [9] M.M. Swisdak, *Explosion effects and properties: part II - explosion effects in water.*, Naval surface weapons centre, Dahlgren, VA, USA, 1978.
- [10] A. Schiffer, V.L. Tagarielli, The response of rigid plates to blast in deep water: fluid-structure interaction experiments, *P. Roy. Soc. Lond. A Mat.*, 468 (2012) 2807-2828.
- [11] E.H. Kennard, Cavitation in an elastic liquid, *Phys. Rev.*, 63 (1943) 172-181.
- [12] A. Schiffer, V.L. Tagarielli, N. Petrinic, A.F.C. Cocks, The Response of Rigid Plates to Deep Water Blast: Analytical Models and Finite Element Predictions, *J. Appl. Mech.*, 79 (2012).